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THE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SCIENCE SUBJECT AND THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The widespread embracing of social media platforms inspires researchers to examine the extent of influence on the academic performance in science class by senior high school students of a private secondary school using purposive sampling to collect empirical data through a survey questionnaire with a Likert scale. Using IBM SPSS statistical package and Micro Soft Excel software, the mean percentage scores and Pearson r indicate that YouTube moderately inspired them and least from Facebook and TikTok for their grades. Besides, Facebook and YouTube moderately influenced their attendance in class, while TikTok had very little. Correlation analysis implies that, albeit not significantly, social media does have an impact on students' attendance; nonetheless, it does not affect their marks.

Keywords: social media, academic performance, science subject, influence

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, social media platforms have penetrated deeply into the mechanics of everyday life, affecting people's informal interactions (Van Dijck & Poell, 2013). This means anybody may get information online by networking with each other. The investigation of Forbush & Foucault-Welles (2016) on Chinese students studying in the United States establishes that diverse social networks are ideal for increasing international students' adaptation the reason why more diverse social networks reported significantly higher levels of social and academic adaptation.

The inquiry made by Maweu & Yuda (2020) in Pakistan reveals that despite the lack of local, reliable research, new media have an impact on university

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students, both positively and negatively but without authentic studies locally. Likewise, Hasnain, Nasreen, and Ijaz (2015) conclude, in the same country, that with advancements in technology and an increase in internet usage, social media has become a part of their daily lives.

For Sudha and Kavitha (2016), social networking sites have drawn a lot of interest from academics and educators because of their rising popularity among students and their potential effects on academic achievement. Also, social media use has become prevalent and nearly inevitable, changing the way students interact, connect, and socialize; it has become an integral part of their social and cultural fabric (Espiritu et al., 2021).

Besides, (Shtern et al. (2019) imply that social media influence work in the Philippines is defined by globally connected but locally rooted practices of performed authenticity through which creators employ conscious and identifiable strategies to cultivate a local audience.

Locally, the study of Cerado (2021) on the employability of graduates, and the media, among others, is one of the relevant skills students explicitly acquired from Sultan Kudarat State University.

Therefore, it is desired that a supplemental concept may be achieved from this study as the motivating factor of the researchers to share consciousness of social media, in particular, Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube on science students as Mulawarman, et al (2020) recognize internet as a mass communication tool that constantly evolve with the times of which Osharive (2015) claimed that a lot of parents, educators, guardians, students, and people are worried about how to help their pupils improve their academic performance.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The study concentrates on the academic performance of senior high school students in science class and how significantly social media influences them. Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok are the social media sites being discussed here. This is supported by a causal-chain framework as suggested by Ngai et al., (2015) as a comprehensive literature review of social media research contributing to a better understanding of the causes and effects of the adoption and usage of social media.

Qiu et al. (2018) define causal chains (variously called logic models, log frames, conceptual models, result chains, or theory of change) as an approach to identifying logical and ordered sequences of effects on how a system responds to interventions, actions, or perturbations.

Guided by the proposition expressing no relationship between using social media platforms to the academic performance of senior high school students in science subjects, the evaluation for the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that

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social media has an impact on student's academic achievement using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Coefficient or Pearson r with the aid of Micro Soft Excel software and IBM SPSS statistical package. This outcome negates with Sharma & Behl (2022) who found a significant difference between extraversion and introversion students for the impact of social media on their academic performance using a one-way ANOVA test.

The graph below describes the relationship of independent variables, which is the use of social media, and its effects on the academic performance of senior high school students in terms of grade, and attendance to classes hung as the dependent variables.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the study

METHODOLOGY

Purposive sampling was used to gather empirical data from 159 senior high school students at a private secondary school through a survey questionnaire with a Likert scale to determine the extent of influence of social media on their academic performance.

This study used a correlational design for examining the relationships among variables in a single group, which could occur at several levels (Devi & Lepcha, 2023), computed through a Pearson Product Moment of Correlation Coefficient using a 0.05 level of significance as a statistical tool. Descriptive statistics such as frequency count, mean, percent, and rank are further utilized to analyze the data of the study as Nneoma et al. (2023) consider that good research should be well-adjusted, well-planned, suitably constructed, and ethically accepted.

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RESULTS

The results of the statistical analysis and interpretation of findings are presented in tables following the sequence of the specific research problem regarding the influence of social media on the academic performance of senior high school students in science subjects.

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA

The tables below elucidate the influence of social media on senior high school students taking science subjects.

A. Attendance to class

Table 1

Facebook's Influence on senior high school student's attendance in class

What is the Influence of Facebook on the attendance of a class of senior high school students?	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
Facebook positively affects my study routine and I rarely attend science lectures.	2.41	5	Very Least Influenced
I occasionally attend lectures even when I often use Facebook.	2.75	2	Neither Influenced
I don't spend the majority of my time on Facebook because I attend class early	2.83	1	Moderately Influenced
I attended about half of the lectures even when I often used Facebook	2.63	4	Moderately Influenced
I have unlimited access to Facebook improved my presence in class.	2.69	3	Moderately Influenced
Overall Weighted Mean Rating	2.66		Moderately Influenced

According to Table 1, the respondents rated the argument that they don't have to spend most of their time on Facebook the highest rating since they have to arrive early for class. This argument received a mean rating score of 2.83, which is interpreted as neither influenced.

The statement on the positive effects of Facebook on the students' study routine and rare attendance to science class lectures is rated least by the

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respondents based on a 2.41 mean rating score interpreted as Very Least Influenced. These data justify that students should not spend a lot of time on Facebook for they need to have an early class attendance and besides this social media flat form does not have positive effects on their study routine and class attendance.

Moreover, the responses on occasional attendance to lectures even if they have to use Facebook gain a 2.75 mean percentage score interpreted as neither. The statement on their capability to attend about half of the lecture even when they have of using Facebook often gathered 2.63 mean scores while their unlimited access to Facebook has improved their presence in class evidenced by a 2.69 mean percentage score, all interpreted as neither.

Still, the overall influence of Facebook as a social media on the academic performance of senior high school students is interpreted as moderately influenced resulting from a 2.66 overall weighted mean rating. This finding agrees with Kabre & Brown (2011) that the number of hours per week spent on Facebook did not predict academic performance.

Table 2

YouTube's Influence on senior high school student's attendance in class

What is the Influence of YouTube on the attendance to class of senior high school students?	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
YouTube positively affects my study routine and I rarely attend science lectures.	2.72	5	Moderately Influenced
I occasionally attend lectures even when I often use YouTube.	2.82	4	Moderately Influenced
I don't spend the majority of my time on YouTube because I attend class early.	2.89	2	Moderately Influenced
I have attended science lectures even when I often used YouTube.	2.92	1	Moderately Influenced
I usually have unlimited access to YouTube and this improved my presence in class.	2.85	3	Moderately Influenced
Overall Weighted Mean Rating	2.84		Moderately Influenced

The results are displayed in Table 2, where it can be observed that the respondents' highest perception, with a weighted mean of 2.92, is that they have attended science lectures while frequently using YouTube. This first rank was evaluated as moderately influenced.

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The lowest rating of the respondents in the arguments that YouTube positively affects their study routine is that they rarely attend science lectures which obtains a mean rating score of 2.72 interpreted as moderately influenced. These data explain that students should have attended science lectures even when using YouTube as well as this social media platform positively affects their study routine as they rarely attend science lectures.

Furthermore, the responses on their unlimited access to YouTube has improved their presence in science class gaining a 2.85 mean percentage score interpreted as moderately influenced. The statement on occasional attendance to science lectures even they have to use YouTube often gathered 2.82 mean scores whereas they don't have to spend the majority of their time on YouTube for they have to attend early to their classes which obtains a mean rating score of 2.89, meaning moderately influenced. Nonetheless, the overall influence of YouTube as a social media on the academic performance of senior high school students is interpreted as moderately influenced resulting from a 2.84 overall weighted mean rating. The result goes with the findings of Bardakci (2019) which suggests that students intend to use YouTube to improve their academic performance.

Table 3

TikTok's Influence on senior high school student's attendance in class

What is the influence of TikTok on the attendance to class of senior high school students?	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
TikTok positively affects my study routine and I rarely attend science lectures.	2.42	5	Very Least Influenced
I occasionally attend lectures even when I often use TikTok	2.6	4	Moderately Influenced
I don't spend the majority of my time on TikTok because I attend class early.	2.73	1	Moderately Influenced
I have attended about half of the lectures even when I often used TikTok.	2.61	2	Moderately Influenced
I usually have unlimited access to TikTok and this has improved my presence in class.	2.54	3	Very Least Influenced
Overall Weighted Mean Rating	2.58		Very Least Influenced

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The result of the evaluation of the impact of social media, that is, TikTok on student's academic achievement is shown in Table 3. The responses indicating that respondents don't spend the majority of their time on TikTok because they must arrive early for their classes receive the highest ratings from the respondents, with a mean rating score of 2.73, which is regarded as moderately influenced. Based on a mean rating score of 2.42, read as very least influenced, the respondents stated the benefits of TikTok of the student's study schedule and occasional attendance to science class lectures to have the lowest rating. The data collected support the idea that students should not spend a lot of time on Facebook since they need to arrive for class early and thus using this type of social media has no beneficial influence on their study habits or attendance.

Additionally, the comments regarding their unlimited use of Facebook have enhanced their participation in class as revealed by a 2.54 mean percentage score that is viewed as having the least influence. The statement about their ability to attend science lectures even when they frequently use TikTok received 2.61 mean scores, while the statement about their ability to occasionally attend lectures even when they frequently use TikTok gained a 2.6 mean percentage score, all of which were interpreted as somewhat influenced. However, based on a 2.58 total weighted mean rating, it is concluded that TikTok's overall influence on senior high school students' academic achievement is relatively minimal. This finding is related to the study of Imaikop & Clement (2023) which recommends that the students be enlightened more on how to utilize TikTok for academic activity improvement.

B. Grade

As presented, Table 4 shows the influence of Facebook on academic performance in terms of grades of senior high school students. The highest rating of the respondents corresponds to relying upon information attained from Facebook concerning science assignments without consulting any other sources which acquires a mean rating score of 2.80 interpreted as moderately influenced. The claim of the respondents that their unlimited access to Facebook has affected their grades in science subjects is based on a 2.42 mean rating score interpreted as very least influenced. These data proved that students should rely on Facebook information about their science assignments without catering to any other sources, however, their unlimited access to Facebook has affected their grades in science subjects.

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Table 4

Facebook's influence on the grade of senior high school students

What is the influence of Facebook on the grades of the senior high school students?	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
I usually have unlimited access to Facebook and this has affected my grades in science subjects.	2.42	5	Very Least Influenced
I engage in science discussions on Facebook has improved my grades in science subjects.	2.56	3	Very Least Influenced
I solely rely on the information obtained from Facebook to do my assignments without consulting other sources.	2.80	1	Very Least Influenced
Engaging in science forums on Facebook reduces my rate of understanding.	2.61	2	Moderately Influenced
I use materials from Facebook to complement what I have been taught in class.	2.56	4	Very Least Influenced
Overall Weighted Mean Rating	2.59		Very Least Influenced

Furthermore, the statement that engaging in science discussions on Facebook has improved the students' grades in science subjects as well as using educational materials from Facebook that complement what students have been taught in science class often collected a 2.56 mean percentage score interpreted to have the very least influence. The responses on engaging in science lectures on Facebook reduce students' rate of understanding gains a 2.61 mean percentage score that is interpreted as a moderate influence. Based on the 2.59 as the overall weighted mean rating, the findings correspond to having the very least influence of Facebook in the grades of senior high school students.

Nevertheless, the study by Thuseethan & Kuhanesan (2014) on the academic performance of Sri Lankan University students using Facebook reveals that it leads to several problems in university students' academic performances.

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Table 5

YouTube's influence on the grade of senior high school students

What is the Influence of YouTube on the grades of senior high school students?	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
I usually have unlimited access to YouTube and this has affected my grades in science subject.	2.86	3	Moderately Influenced
I engage in science discussions on YouTube and has improved my grades in science subjects.	2.84	4	Moderately Influenced
I solely rely on information from YouTube to do my assignments without consulting from other sources.	2.88	2	Moderately Influenced
Engaging in science forums on YouTube reduces my rate of understanding.	2.93	1	Moderately Influenced
I use materials from YouTube to complement what I have been taught in class.	2.82	5	Moderately Influenced
Overall Weighted Mean Rating	2.87		Moderately Influenced

Table 5 explains that the highest rating of the respondents is on the claim that engaging in science lectures on YouTube reduces the student's rate of understanding which gains a mean rating score of 2.93 interpreted as moderately influenced. The contention of the use of educational materials from YouTube to complement what the students have been taught in science class is rated as moderately influenced by the respondents based on a 2.82 mean rating score. These data validate that students should not engage in science lectures on YouTube as it reduces the student's rate of understanding and the use of educational materials.

In addition, the responses on the unlimited access to YouTube have affected the students' grades in science subjects gains a 2.86 mean score rating, also engaging in science discussion on YouTube has improved the students' grades in science subject have obtained a 2.84 mean percentage rating as well as relying on the information got from YouTube to do the students assignment without consulting

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other sources attain a 2.88 mean percentage score, all interpreted as moderately influenced.

Nevertheless, the overall influence of YouTube as a social media platform on the academic performance of senior high school students is interpreted as moderately influenced resulting from a 2.87 overall weighted mean rating. The result agrees with the suggestion of Bidarra & Sousa (2020) who suggest that students intend to use YouTube to improve their academic performance

Table 6
TikTok's influence on the grade of senior high school students

What is the Influence of TikTok on the grades of senior high school students?	Weighted Mean	Rank	Verbal Interpretation
I usually have unlimited access to TikTok and this has affected my grades in science subject.	2.16	5	Very least influenced
I engage in science discussions on TikTok and has improved my grades in science subject.	2.6	3	Very least influenced
I solely rely on information from TikTok to do my assignments without consulting other sources.	2.56	4	Very least influenced
Engaging in science forums on TikTok reduces my rate of understanding.	2.69	2	Moderately Influenced
I use materials from TikTok to complement what I have been taught in class.	2.87	1	Moderately Influenced
Overall Weighted Mean Rating	2.43		Very least influenced

Table 6 illustrates that the highest rating of the respondents is on the argument that the use of educational materials found on TikTok that complement what the students have been taught in science class got a mean rating score of 2.87 interpreted as moderately influenced. The statement on the unlimited access to TikTok that has affected the students' grades in science subjects was rated to have the very least influence based on the 2.16 mean rating score. These data confirm that the students should use the educational materials found on TikTok that will complement what they have been taught in science class. However, unlimited access to TikTok has been proven the effect to the student's grades.

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Besides, the responses on engaging in science lectures on TikTok reduced students' rate of understanding and obtained a 2.69 mean percentage score interpreted as a moderate influence. The statement that their engagement in science discussion on TikTok has improved their grades in science subjects gathered 2.6 mean scores on the other hand, relying on the information found on TikTok to do their science assignments without consulting any other sources collected a 2.56 mean percentage score, all interpreted to have a very least influenced.

The overall influence of TikTok as a social media platform on the academic performance of senior high school students is interpreted to have the very least influence resulting from a 2.43 overall weighted mean rating. This finding is comparable to the conclusion of Herath (2020) that even though TikTok has a positive impact on a student's mental health and creativity, watching and posting TikTok Videos are time-consuming activities and thus have a negative impact on students' academic achievements.

Correlational analysis showing the relationship between attendance and grades on students' academic performance as influenced by social media

The correlational analysis showing the relationship between attendance and grades on students' academic performance is summarized in Table 7. The study utilizes the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Coefficient or Pearson r to estimate and test the significance of the simple linear correlation coefficient r , which is the measure of the degree or strength of linear association or relationship between two variables represented by X and Y with the aid of Micro Soft Excel software and IBM SPSS statistical package.

The independent variable X is the attendance related to students' academic performance as influenced by social media. On the other hand, the dependent variable Y is the grade related to the student's academic performance as influenced by social media.

The summary of the statistical treatment of the variables shows a strong correlation coefficient r of 0.706. This interpretation is based on the table of conventional approach to interpreting a correlation coefficient presented by Schober & Schwarte (2018).

Since there is a linear relationship between the variables, hypothesis testing is conducted to find out the significance of the correlation coefficient. The level of significance $\alpha = 0.05 > p\text{-value} = 0.003$ and $t = 3.597 > t(\text{tab}) = \pm 2.16$. Since α is greater than the significance value ($p\text{-value}$) and the computed $t\text{-test}$ value of 3.597 falls outside the acceptance region of the normal curve, signifies that the null

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hypothesis H_0 must be rejected which means that there is a Significant Relationship between the Attendance (X) and Grade (Y). The decision for the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the student's academic performance is influenced by social media.

Truly, this empirical finding opposes Tafesse (2020) emphasizing that student engagement mediates the negative association between social networking site use and college students' academic performance.

Moreover, the coefficient of determination $r^2 = 0.498$ implies that 49.8% of the variation in the grade related to the student's academic performance as influenced by social media is attributed to attendance related to the student's grade. Consequently, the evidence shows that the null hypothesis - which states that social media has no bearing on a student's grade - is thus rejected.

The same result coincides with the study of Nwoburuoke & Eremie (2021) in River State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria declaring that the use of Facebook, Whatsapp, and YouTube can influence academic performance of students.

Table 7

Relationship between the attendance and grade on student's academic performance as influenced by social media.

R	Correlation Coefficient r	r^2	Level of Significance α	Sig. p -value	Critical Value $t (tab)$	t -Test Value	Decision	Relationship
0.706	Strong Correlation	0.498	0.05	0.003	± 2.16	3.597	Reject H_0	Significant

Legend: Strength of Correlation by Schober & Schwarte (2018): 0.00-0.10 Negligible Correlation, 0.10-0.39 Weak Correlation, 0.40-0.69 Moderate Correlation, 0.70-0.89 Strong Correlation, 0.90-0.1 Very Strong Correlation

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DISCUSSION

The focus of this paper is to ascertain the level of responses of senior high school students on the influence of social media, in particular, Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok on their academic performance in science subjects and which factor of social media influences academic performance pegged as the attendance to class and grade.

Based on the collected data, it showed that Facebook moderately influenced students' attendance to class while having the very least influence on the grade. It can be inferred that although there is a moderate factor of influence to come to school, the least effect on their grades.

YouTube has a complementary moderate influence on students' attendance in class and their grades. TikTok, however, is least influential to both their attendance and grades. The result justifies that YouTube has moderately influenced the attendance to class and the grades of the senior high school students while less from TikTok.

Moving further, resulting from a correlational analysis, the hypothesis rejected that social media has no bearing on students' attendance to class and grades on their academic performance. Social media does not influence attendance to class and grades for senior high school students towards their academic performance.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Social media has varied degrees of influence on both the attendance and grades of senior high school students in science subjects. Facebook and YouTube moderately influenced attendance to class, while TikTok has very little.

In terms of the influence of social media on the grades of the students, it is YouTube that moderately inspired them and least from Facebook and TikTok.

The correlational analysis reveals that social media does impact attendance to some extent but has no bearing on students' grades, although the influence is not overwhelmingly strong.

Therefore, in the light of the findings and conclusion of this study, the following are strongly recommended:

1. Teachers must be cautious about how they utilize social media in their classrooms to help children do better academically.

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2. The use of social media can be a distraction in class; therefore, students should avoid it and better organize their study time. Students should spend less time online.
3. Students should utilize social media networks for academic objectives rather than for undesirable ones.
4. Students need to appreciate how social media affects their academic performance.
5. Teachers and parents should monitor their students on how they utilize social media platforms.

FURTHER STUDY

Delve into what other factors in social media may be fruitful for students' attendance in science class and improve their grades.

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